
UnLIR

Plan de gestion de données créé à l'aide de DMP OPIDoR

Créateur du PGD : ronan sicre

Affiliation du créateur principal : Ecole Centrale de MARSEILLE

Modèle du PGD : ANR - DMP template (english)

Dernière modification du PGD : 11/10/2021

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Résumé du projet :

UnLIR: Unsupervised Learning of Image Representation is a young researcher ANR project coordinated by Ronan Sicre starting in January 2020 and ending in April 2024.

The project deals with latent representation learning for complex recognition tasks, such as fine-grained recognition; Unsupervised representation learning; and interpretability of deep neural Networks.

The Team is composed of Thierry Artières (LIS), Stephane Ayache (LIS), Yannis Avrithis (INRIA Rennes) and Ronan Sicre (LIS).

Chercheur Principal : Ronan Sicre

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1. Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

1a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

During our research, existing public dataset are used.
However, no new data is collected or produced as part of this project.

1b. What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

No data will be collected or produced as part of this project.
Only publications and software will be produced, which will be made available for scientific research purpose.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

RDA DMP common standard will be applied. Moreover FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interperable, and Reusable) principle will be respected.

2b. What data quality control measures will be used?

Concerning software, program are tested, debugged and a read me presenting the software, its requirement, as well as usage example will be made available.

Concerning publication, accepted publications in conference of journals are peer reviewed.

3. Storage and backup during the research process

3a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

The DMP will be stored on Zenodo, with DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5562249

3b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care during the research

not applicable.

4. Legal and ethical requirements, code of conduct

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

not applicable.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

The produced software will be open access and will use a common creative licence CC-BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 international).

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

not applicable.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

Publication will be made publicly available after acceptance.

5b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

Publication will be shared on HAL or Arxiv.
The laboratory Github will be used to share code.

5c. What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

not applicable.

5d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

DOI will be given to publication upon demand of the conferences or journals.

6. Data management responsibilities and resources

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

The projects PI will be managing the data

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

No specific resources are dedicated to data management.

Appendix

This appendix list all the published data:

Ayache, Stephane, Ronan Sire, and Thierry Artières. "Transfer Learning by Weighting Convolution." *International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*. 2020.
<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02544099/>